

On the social and cognitive dimensions of wicked environmental problems characterized by conceptual and solution uncertainty

Felber Arroyave¹, Oscar Yandy Romero Goyeneche², Meredith Gore³, Gaston Heimeriks⁴, Jeffrey Jenkins¹, Alexander Petersen¹.

1. Management of Complex Systems Department, Ernest and Julio Gallo Management Program, School of Engineering, University of California, Merced, CA 95343, U.S.
2. Utrecht University Centre for Global Challenges, the Netherlands
3. Department of Geographical Sciences, University of Maryland, College Park, MD, 20742 U.S.
4. Copernicus Institute of Sustainable Development, Utrecht University, the Netherlands

We develop a quantitative framework for understanding the class of wicked problems that emerge at the intersections of “natural”, social, and technological complex systems. Wicked problems reflect our incomplete understanding of interdependent global systems and the systemic risk they pose; such problems escape solutions because they are often ill-defined, and thus mis-identified and under-appreciated by communities of problem-solvers. While there are well-documented benefits to tackling boundary-crossing problems from various viewpoints, the integration of diverse approaches can nevertheless contribute confusion around the collective understanding of the core concepts and feasible solutions. We explore this paradox by analyzing the development of both scholarly and topical communities within three wicked problems: deforestation, invasive species, and wildlife trade. We posit that saturation in the dynamics of social and cognitive diversity growth is an indicator of reduced uncertainty in the evolution of the comprehensive knowledge trajectory emerging around each wicked problem. Informed by comprehensive bibliometric data capturing both social and cognitive dimensions of each problem domain, we thereby develop a framework that assesses the stability of knowledge trajectory dynamics as an indicator of wickedness associated with conceptual and solution uncertainty. As such, our results identify wildlife trade as a wicked problem that may be difficult to address given recent instability in its knowledge trajectory.

Keywords: Knowledge trajectory, knowledge integration, knowledge networks, collaboration networks, relatedness, diversity.

Supplementary Notes

Supplementary note 1. Search queries.

The information for each case study was collected in November 2020 using specific queries aimed at capturing the publications related to each case up to date. We performed an iterative procedure in which we include different combinations of keywords for each case with the purpose of identifying an optimal query that warrants the retrieval of most of the publications associated to the problem and reduces possible sources of misidentification such as unrelated publications given synonyms. Overall, we identify that for deforestation and invasive species general queries (i.e., $TS=("deforest*"); TS=("invasive" NEAR/3 "species")$) are able to capture most of the research in that domains without the intrusion of unrelated research. In contrast, simple queries for wildlife trade (e.g., "wildlife trade") retrieved unrelated publications (e.g., economy and trade of other commodities) and incomplete results. The inclusion of synonyms of wildlife trade (i.e., 'wildlife traffic and/or wildlife trafficking') resulted in the intrusion of publications related to animal transit in driveways and corridors. We therefore design a more complex query (i.e., $TS=("wildlife trad*" OR "wildlife traff*" OR "trade of wildlife" OR "trade on wildlife" OR "wildlife market")$) which reduce the amount of unrelated research and provides a comprehensive compendium of publications that include any of the variants used by researchers to refer to wildlife trade.

Supplementary note 2. Co-bibliography network's construction

One of the most frequent and powerful approaches for understanding dynamics of science is the bibliometric analysis, which frequently relies on the use of networks as analytic representation of the underlying structures of science. Network analysis is leveraged by a systematic and relational approach that accounts for knowledge integration and interaction across different domains, including collaboration, citation, use of language (i.e., co-keywords usage), among many other. Of particular interest in this work are the co-bibliography networks (CBN), which use bibliography coupling distances to relate publications in terms of their cognitive and semantic structures (Grauwin & Jensen, 2011). CBN are therefore composed by nodes (publications) and links that connect them reflecting their bibliography similarity. The proximity between nodes in CBN indicates that authors are using and reading similar literatures as well as are addressing a common problem throughout similar lenses from either the methodological or conceptual standpoint.

In our study we build up the CBN using the bibliographic elements associated to each publication or source as they are reported by Web of Science (WoS). We calculate the bibliographic coupling between sources using the measure proposed by Grauwin & Jensen (2011), which bases in the proportion of references shared between sources over the length of the joint references pool. As such, the bibliographic coupling varies between 0 (no coupling) and 1 (full coupling). We therefore construct a matrix that associate each source with the other through their cognitive distance. Such matrix is then a mathematical representation of the network. However, within the pool of interactions across the matrix not all of them must be considered as part of the network, but only those that consistently indicate meaningful cognitive association (Palacios-Núñez et al., 2018).

In order to identify the set of meaningful links as well as the core of coherent publications we follow Ramirez et al. (2019) strategy of modularity maximization. To this end, we iteratively define a threshold below which links are considered as non-informative. For the network generated we then calculate the modularity using Louvain algorithm for community finding, excluding from the analysis all the nodes that became disconnected when the threshold was traced. Given that in the network frequently dyads and small sub-clusters are generated, which inflates the modularity, we remove any sub-cluster and community of smaller size than 10 nodes, and then the modularity is re-calculated. As a result of the increase in threshold value, the network becomes smaller, more modular, and the number of communities varies in an inverted 'u' shape, as we show in Fig. a below. For each study case included in this work we determine the threshold for meaningfulness as the value at which we maximize the modularity, the number of communities in the network, and minimize the number of nodes lost, as it is shown in Fig. a.

Figure a. Modularity maximization in co-bibliography networks of the research on deforestation (orange), invasive species (brown), and wildlife trade (purple). Maximization is conducted by considering variation in nodes (left), communities (central), and modularity (right). The defined thresholds are indicated with vertical dashed lines.

The result of the maximization of the network is shown in Supplementary figure 1. The networks were optimized at different threshold values (deforestation=0.167; invasive species=0.177; wildlife trade=0.181), though similar between them, resulting in networks highly modular (deforestation=; invasive species=; wildlife trade=). Although the networks are in many cases composed by multiple components, all of them are characterized by a dominant (giant) component that harbors most of the communities.

Supplementary Figures

SF. 1. Co-bibliography networks for the 3 case studies addressed in the study. (a) deforestation, (a) invasive species, and (c) wildlife trade

SF1a. Co-bibliography network of publications related to deforestation. Nodes are publications and links represent the bibliographic coupling. Nodes are colored according to the modules or communities of knowledge found by Louvain modularity algorithm. In the left subpanels is shown the composition of the network at different time frames, each one including a third of the nodes, approximately. In the right panel is shown the network with all the nodes. The network is composed by 12500 nodes and 76 communities of knowledge. Links are defined using 0.167 as the lower end of bibliographic coupling producing a modularity equal to 0.882.

SF1b. Co-bibliography network of publications related to invasive species. Nodes are publications and links represent the bibliographic coupling. Nodes are colored according to the modules or communities of knowledge found by Louvain modularity algorithm. In the left subpanels is shown the composition of the network at different time frames, each one including a third of the nodes, approximately. In the right panel is shown the network with all the nodes. The network is composed by 15712 nodes and 117 communities of knowledge. Links are defined using 0.177 as the lower end of bibliographic coupling producing a modularity equal to 0.946.

SF1c. Co-bibliography network of publications related to wildlife trade. Nodes are publications and links represent the bibliographic coupling. Nodes are colored according to the modules or communities of knowledge found by Louvain modularity algorithm. In the left subpanels is shown the composition of the network at different time frames, each one including a third of the nodes, approximately. In the right panel is shown the network with all the nodes. The network is composed by 655 nodes and 24 communities of knowledge. Links are defined using 0.181 as the lower end of bibliographic coupling producing a modularity equal to 0.848.

Dynamics of knowledge trajectories measured as Shannon-Evenness.

SF2. Intra-annual distribution of diversity of publications in 3 domains of research: deforestation (red), invasive species (golden), wildlife trade (purple). Diversity is considered as the disparity of frequencies of the different components for each variable. The disparity is then measured as the Shannon-evenness index of (a) communities of knowledge, (b) WoS subject categories, (c) Country of the institutions in which authors are affiliated, (d) Journal of publication, (e) Authors, (f) co-authorship dyads, (g) keywords, (h) co-keywords dyads, (i) Global South and Global North differentiation of countries associated to authors. Solid lines represent the empirical data and shades interquartile range of the random model.

SF3. Intra-annual variation of the differences between the empirical diversity of publications and random models for 3 domains of research: deforestation (red), invasive species (golden), wildlife trade (purple). Diversity is considered as the disparity of frequencies of the different components for each variable. The disparity is then measured as the Shannon-evenness index of (a) communities of knowledge, (b) WoS subject categories, (c) Country of the institutions in which authors are affiliated, (d) Journal of publication, (e) Authors, (f) co-authorship dyads, (g) keywords, (h) co-keywords dyads, (i) Global South and Global North differentiation of countries associated to authors. Shades correspond to the interquartile range of the difference between empirical data and the random model.

SF4. Cumulative or inter-annual distribution of diversity of publications in 3 domains of research: deforestation (red), invasive species (golden), wildlife trade (purple). Diversity is considered as the disparity of frequencies of the different components for each variable. The disparity is then measured as the Shannon-evenness index of (a) communities of knowledge, (b) WoS subject categories, (c) Country of the institutions in which authors are affiliated, (d) Journal of publication, (e) Authors, (f) co-authorship dyads, (g) keywords, (h) co-keywords dyads, (i) Global South and Global North differentiation of countries associated to authors. Solid lines represent the empirical data and shades interquartile range of the random model.

SF5. Cumulative or intra-annual variation of the differences between the empirical diversity of publications and random models for 3 domains of research: deforestation (red), invasive species (golden), wildlife trade (purple). Diversity is considered as the disparity of frequencies of the different components for each variable. The disparity is then measured as the Shannon-evenness index of (a) communities of knowledge, (b) WoS subject categories, (c) Country of the institutions in which authors are affiliated, (d) Journal of publication, (e) Authors, (f) co-authorship dyads, (g) keywords, (h) co-keywords dyads, (i) Global South and Global North differentiation of countries associated to authors. Shades correspond to the interquartile range of the difference between empirical data and the random model.

Dynamics of knowledge trajectories measured as Gini complement.

SF6. Intra-annual distribution of diversity of publications in 3 domains of research: deforestation (red), invasive species (golden), wildlife trade (purple). Diversity is considered as the disparity of frequencies of the different components for each variable. The disparity is then measured as the Gini index of (a) communities of knowledge, (b) WoS subject categories, (c) Country of the institutions in which authors are affiliated, (d) Journal of publication, (e) Authors, (f) co-authorship dyads, (g) keywords, (h) co-keywords dyads, (i) Global South and Global North differentiation of countries associated to authors. Solid lines represent the empirical data and shades interquartile range of the random model.

SF7. Intra-annual variation of the differences between the empirical diversity of publications and random models for 3 domains of research: deforestation (red), invasive species (golden), wildlife trade (purple). Diversity is considered as the disparity of frequencies of the different components for each variable. The disparity is then measured as the Gini index of (a) communities of knowledge, (b) WoS subject categories, (c) Country of the institutions in which authors are affiliated, (d) Journal of publication, (e) Authors, (f) co-authorship dyads, (g) keywords, (h) co-keywords dyads, (i) Global South and Global North differentiation of countries associated to authors. Shades correspond to the interquartile range of the difference between empirical data and the random model.

SF8. Cumulative or inter-annual distribution of diversity of publications in 3 domains of research: deforestation (red), invasive species (golden), wildlife trade (purple). Diversity is considered as the disparity of frequencies of the different components for each variable. The disparity is then measured as the Gini index of (a) communities of knowledge, (b) WoS subject categories, (c) Country of the institutions in which authors are affiliated, (d) Journal of publication, (e) Authors, (f) co-authorship dyads, (g) keywords, (h) co-keywords dyads, (i) Global South and Global North differentiation of countries associated to authors. Solid lines represent the empirical data and shades interquartile range of the random model.

SF9. Cumulative or intra-annual variation of the differences between the empirical diversity of publications and random models for 3 domains of research: deforestation (red), invasive species (golden), wildlife trade (purple). Diversity is considered as the disparity of frequencies of the different components for each variable. The disparity is then measured as the Gini index of (a) communities of knowledge, (b) WoS subject categories, (c) Country of the institutions in which authors are affiliated, (d) Journal of publication, (e) Authors, (f) co-authorship dyads, (g) keywords, (h) co-keywords dyads, (i) Global South and Global North differentiation of countries associated to authors. Shades correspond to the interquartile range of the difference between empirical data and the random model.